

Pricing framework to foster global equity in scholarly publishing

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informationpower

July 19, 2024

Commissioned by
cOAlition S

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Introduction

The transition of academic publishing from the subscription model to open access has shifted payments for publishing services from readers to producers of knowledge. Although this transition makes publications accessible to readers globally, unaffordable pricing limits the ability of many authors to publish open access. Pricing practices in publishing models do not currently serve regional and global equity (OASPA 2024¹).

Article Processing Charge (APC) waivers and discounts are often used to make the system fairer and, while appreciated, have also triggered significant concerns, as practices differ widely and can be confusing. Waivers are sometimes seen as a form of charity and viewed as intrinsically opaque, condescending, and undermining solidarity in the global research

¹ See <https://www.oaspa.org/news/oaspa-calls-for-community-feedback-on-draft-recommendations-to-increase-equity-in-open-access/> for full background and a terrific list of further reading.

community. They are a mechanism unilaterally controlled by publishers and do not afford any agency to the stakeholders who are paying for publishing services.

The practice of charging different prices in different countries is widespread, but does *not* necessarily result in affordable or equitable access. For example, a business might use differentiated global pricing to maximize profits rather than to improve equity.

[cOAlition S](#) commissioned [Information Power](#) to explore how a globally fairer pricing framework for academic publishing could be devised and implemented. The key objective of this study was to identify ways in which readers and producers of scholarly publications or their proxies – research funders and universities – could financially contribute to supporting the academic publishing services valued by their research communities, as a function of their means, in a manner that is more equitable and sustainable.

As this is a complicated area – and price is a matter on which publishers can, and should, compete – this framework is introduced to enable discussion and to facilitate more equitable pricing practices. We seek to inspire publishers (and other service providers) to implement more equitable pricing, and provide guiding principles, data, models, and tools to help them. This pricing framework to foster global equity can be used wherever fees are charged – for example with APCs, membership fees, subscriptions, or transformative and open access agreements.

This is a forward step on our shared journey toward more equitable pricing. The proposed framework cannot solve all problems, and we anticipate that waivers will still be needed in some cases. For example, there can be particular challenges related to equity within countries², across disciplines, or for early-career researchers. Funders, libraries, consortia, and institutional leaders all have a role to play in developing coordinated approaches and locally appropriate cost distribution models to reduce inequities among researchers.

Implementing this global pricing framework to foster equity in scholarly publishing can advance the community toward greater diversity, equity, inclusion, belonging, and fairness.

Principles

The principles developed during this project were crafted in discussion with stakeholders, support the [OA2020](#) initiative [Invitation to Action: Collaborating toward globally equitable scholarly journal publishing](#), and provide detail on how to articulate fees associated with open access publishing services in a way that is more globally equitable, [as called for by OASPA](#).

² The pricing framework to foster more global equity in scholarly publishing can be used alongside within-country banding where this is already in use (e.g. Jisc banding for UK universities <https://subscriptionsmanager.jisc.ac.uk/about/jisc-banding> or Research4Life https://portal.research4life.org/country_offer).

Global differentiated pricing that fosters equity is:

- Part of a broader commitment to equity, inclusion, diversity, and belonging. Any concerted effort also requires taking steps to empower and involve historically excluded stakeholders across global regions, institutions, and disciplines.
- Aligned ideally with a single consistent approach developed in meaningful, open, and transparent consultation with the research community (i.e. libraries/consortia, funders, and researchers). For example, while moving to more equitable differentiated global pricing may not be cost-neutral, publishers should consider that offsetting this by simply increasing prices for the wealthiest countries may not be perceived as equitable either.
- Relative to the context of each country, including income and purchasing power.
- Communicated clearly, easy to understand, and transparent to all.
- Transparently based on independent, open datasets that are regularly updated and that can be accessed, validated, and reused by everyone.
- Based on shared risk. For example, currency fluctuation can significantly impact the ability of some customers to pay for publishing services, even if prices are differentiated globally. Customers and publishers should share such risks.

The Pricing Framework to Foster Global Equity

The framework to support publishers (and other service providers) to implement differentiated global pricing in alignment with the principles above consists of:

- Open, transparent data from the World Bank International Comparison Program that reflects each country's income *and* ability to pay.
- A banding model so that countries can be grouped in a manageable way.
- An Excel-based tool so that publishers and service providers can set their own bands and differential prices using the same open, transparent data.
- Analysis to encourage publishers and service providers to issue invoices in the local currency of at least some customers.
- Extensive appendices that describe the wide array of datasets that were considered and dismissed, how to download the dataset from the World Bank website, information about the changes in the World Bank International Comparison Program country indices in the 2017 and 2021 data, and important detailed guidance.

The Data

We explored, considered, and rejected the idea of basing this framework on income data alone. This is because those with the same income can have a very different ability to pay. Think of two families with \$100,000 in income. One of the families has two working parents, one child, a low mortgage, and no debt. The other family has a single working parent, three children, rented accommodation, and extensive debt. These families have the same income but a very different ability to pay.

It is more equitable to charge different prices for the same goods/services based on factors varying by country. To implement this aspiration, we explored a wide array of Purchasing Price Indices (PPIs). Their primary use is as a means of comparison between economies, and they weren't originally envisaged as a tool for *setting* comparative prices³.

Any PPI is derived from a selection of local costs and prices combined in some defined way. Using this as a proxy for the ability to pay for goods or services that are produced or provided elsewhere is just that – a proxy measure, and it is reasonable to expect that different people may have different opinions about how accurate a particular PPI is as a proxy.

If we could somehow have a PPI tailored exactly to the investment in, or costs of, doing research in any country, calibrated to regional wealth variations within countries, and updated daily, this would be ideal. However, there is no such PPI. Even if there were, there would still be any number of other unknown variables; for example, within any given country there could be variations between funders in what they were willing to finance in terms of publication costs, differences between well-resourced and less-well-supported universities, and big differences in support for research in different subject areas.

We evaluated the Big Mac, Eurostat/OECD, ICP/World Bank, Numbeo, and United Nations Statistical Department PPIs on the basis of update frequency, countries covered, methodology, and data quality (see Appendix 1). It quickly became apparent that the ICP/World Bank data was best for our purposes. Its coverage – 192 countries – is by far the broadest. While the Numbeo index has data for c. 85 countries, this is skewed toward the richest cities in those countries.

The next challenge to overcome was that there is not one single ICP/World Bank PPI but rather a series of 47 different PPIs, of which 11 (those ticked below) looked relevant to our cause:

³ Note that vocabulary is not settled, and in the footnotes to this report you will encounter varied acronyms and diversity in how shared acronyms are expanded. Further context is provided at this link, but note that they use PPPs where we use PPP, and PLIs where we use PPI: https://www.worldbank.org/en/programs/icp/brief/VC_Uses.

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1000000:GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT | <input type="checkbox"/> 1101000:FOOD AND NON-ALCOHOLIC BEVERAGES |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1101100:FOOD | <input type="checkbox"/> 1101110:Bread and cereals |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1101120:Meat | <input type="checkbox"/> 1101130:Fish and seafood |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1101140:Milk, cheese and eggs | <input type="checkbox"/> 1101150:Oils and fats |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1101160:Fruit | <input type="checkbox"/> 1101170:Vegetables |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1101180:Sugar, jam, honey, chocolate and confectionery | <input type="checkbox"/> 1101190:Food products n.e.c. (Class) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1101200:NON-ALCOHOLIC BEVERAGES | <input type="checkbox"/> 1102000:ALCOHOLIC BEVERAGES, TOBACCO AND NARCOTICS |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1102100:ALCOHOLIC BEVERAGES | <input type="checkbox"/> 1102200:TOBACCO |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1103000:CLOTHING AND FOOTWEAR | <input type="checkbox"/> 1105000:FURNISHINGS, HOUSEHOLD EQUIPMENT AND ROUTINE HOUSEHOLD MAINTENANCE |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1107000:TRANSPORT | <input type="checkbox"/> 1107100:PURCHASE OF VEHICLES |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1107300:TRANSPORT SERVICES | <input type="checkbox"/> 1108000:COMMUNICATION |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1111000:RESTAURANTS AND HOTELS | <input type="checkbox"/> 1113000:NET PURCHASES ABROAD |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1300000:INDIVIDUAL CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE BY GOVERNMENT | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1400000:COLLECTIVE CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE BY GOVERNMENT |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1500000:GROSS CAPITAL FORMATION | <input type="checkbox"/> 1501000:GROSS FIXED CAPITAL FORMATION |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1501100:MACHINERY AND EQUIPMENT | <input type="checkbox"/> 1501200:CONSTRUCTION |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1501300:OTHER PRODUCTS | <input type="checkbox"/> 1502000:CHANGES IN INVENTORIES |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1503000:ACQUISITIONS LESS DISPOSALS OF VALUABLES (Category) | <input type="checkbox"/> 1600000:BALANCE OF EXPORTS AND IMPORTS |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 9020000:ACTUAL INDIVIDUAL CONSUMPTION | <input type="checkbox"/> 9060000:ACTUAL HOUSING, WATER, ELECTRICITY, GAS AND OTHER FUELS |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 9080000:ACTUAL HEALTH | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 9100000:HOUSEHOLDS AND NPISHS FINAL CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 9110000:ACTUAL RECREATION AND CULTURE | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 9120000:ACTUAL EDUCATION |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 9140000:ACTUAL MISCELLANEOUS GOODS AND SERVICES | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 9250000:DOMESTIC ABSORPTION |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 9260000:INDIVIDUAL CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE BY HOUSEHOLDS WITHOUT HOUSING | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 9270000:GENERAL GOVERNMENT FINAL CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE |
| <input type="checkbox"/> SP.EXCHG.RATE.ICP:Exchange Rate Value | <input type="checkbox"/> SP.POP.TOTL.ICP.ZS:Population shares (World=100) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> SP.POP.TOTL.ICP:Population | |

Having evaluated these 11 PPIs (see Appendix 2), we found many of them too narrow in terms of the economic sectors they covered and felt that the World Bank 9020000 Actual Individual Consumption would perhaps be our preferred PPI. However, we decided to go with the World Bank GDP (i.e. GDP adjusted by purchasing power), as it is not much different in results, it covers a more complete range of countries (192 vs. 177)⁴, it was updated in May 2024⁵ with data through 2021, and it is scheduled to be refreshed on a three-yearly basis in future.

A few points should be noted regarding our application of the World Bank/ICP GDP PPI:

- The figures incorporate both income *and* purchasing power.

⁴ But note that counting countries is not an easy thing to do. The UN recognizes 193 countries + two observers and the Olympic Committee recognizes 206 countries.

⁵ Our consultation draft contained a toolkit based on 2017 data, and the figures and examples in this report are reworked using the new data from 2021 and published in 2024.

- In a very limited number of cases the World Bank has given PPI values to a region within a larger country. In these cases, we set a rule that the country's PPI takes the value of the highest of the PPIs involved. The most significant example here is that of China, where there are separate PPIs available for both Macao and Hong Kong. In this case the Hong Kong figure is the highest, so we have assigned this to China and Macao. It seems reasonable to assume that economic conditions in Chinese urban areas where most research is undertaken are more like those in Hong Kong than they are those in rural China.

- Global data collection often involves significant time lags, meaning that the data may not accurately reflect recent global events. The covid pandemic, for example, impacted different countries at different times. The data for both 2017 and 2021 is presented in Figure 1.

Fig.1. A comparison of the 2021 and 2017 GDP-PPI values

The Bands

Grouping countries together into bands makes sense for the following reasons:

- A limited number of bands is far easier to administer than individual prices for each country.
- Banding introduces stability by ensuring most changes occur within a band.
- Those few countries with no World Bank GDP PPI value can be allocated to the bands with countries most similar in terms of geography and economics.

For an **example** see Figure 2.

Fig. 2. An example of banding based on GDP informed by purchasing power. This example uses six bands. Countries and their banding are on the x-axis and the World Bank GDP PPI values are on the y-axis. Note that we have clustered countries by region for ease of reading.

Setting More Equitable Prices

Prices need to vary across the bands. Countries in the ZETA band have a greater ability to pay than countries in the ALPHA band, and it is fair that they do pay more.

The framework does not compel publishers to charge in every country, it just helps them do so more equitably if they do. Different weightings, for example 0% weightings in the countries with the least ability to pay, could be entirely appropriate.

For new services or straightforward transitions

List prices can then be set as ratios. Here are two examples:

Example 1	Example 2
Zeta = 1.0	Zeta = 1.0
Epsilon = 0.8	Epsilon = 0.8
Delta = 0.5	Delta = 0.5
Gamma = 0.2	Gamma = 0.2
Beta = 0.1	Beta = 0.1
Alpha = 0.05	Alpha = 0

For more complex transitions of existing services

To transition the pricing of existing services, each publisher will need to use the Equitable Pricing Tool to develop bespoke banding. A publisher’s precise mix of revenue streams, the way it deploys discounts and waivers, the geographic distribution and volume of its papers (potentially over a number of years), and the decision to apply more equitable pricing to all customers at once or in a more gradual way will all have a bearing.

This nuance is important. We did a sobering calculation based on the assumption that more equitable pricing based on each country’s PPI-informed-GDP value is deployed for all customers at once, that APC revenue streams are the only revenue streams for the journals in which open access articles are published, and that there will be no increase in the number of articles published because of more equitable pricing⁶. Our analysis indicated that, on average and without banding, list price APCs would need to increase by c. 41% if publishers were to

⁶ We would sound a note of caution to any funders and libraries who might argue that a fairer approach to pricing could enable publishers to increase their customer base – and therefore revenue – without increasing prices for any customer. Publishers are already actively trying to increase submissions and article numbers. Such an expansion would be exceedingly unlikely to plug the gap. A publisher incurs costs for every paper published; the average revenue per paper must exceed this cost if a publisher is to stay in business, and must exceed it sufficiently to allow for continued investment if it is to thrive.

retain their current revenue and implement more equitable pricing for all customers worldwide in one step.

Sensible assumptions and tailored banding can drastically reduce this figure, as is shown in Table 1. It shows worked examples using Dimensions.ai data from four anonymous publishers (two large mixed-model publishers, one medium mixed-model university press, and one medium-sized fully open access publisher).

Examples of banding set-ups	Global	Publisher 1	Publisher 2	Publisher 3	Publisher 4
1. Base case (no banding)	41%	34%	23%	19%	14%
2. Banding in 0.1, mid-points	43%	36%	25%	21%	17%
3. Banding in 0.1, upper limit	33%	27%	18%	13%	11%
4. Bandings in 0.2, band value takes upper limit	25%	20%	12%	7%	6%
5. Bandings in 0.2, band values more nuanced	33%	26%	15%	12%	9%
6. Bandings in 0.2, band values more nuanced (v2)	32%	25%	14%	11%	8%
7. Bandings more finely spaced at top and bottom, wider in middle, bands take top value	28%	23%	13%	9%	7%
8. Bandings in 0.2, upper limit, top band set to 1 (i.e. nobody pays more than the default US rate).	27%	22%	14%	9%	8%

Table 1. Effects of various types of banding. The 'Global' column is for all the publishers in the Dimensions database. We also looked at Dimensions data for four publishers individually: two large mixed-model publishers (Publishers 1 and 2), one medium-sized publisher that is fully open access (Publisher 3), and one medium mixed-model university press (Publisher 4). For each example of banding set-up, the percentages show the proportional uplift that would be required to maintain current revenues.

Precise details of the band boundaries and values used in each example are given in the tables at the end of Appendix 3 (which we strongly recommend publishers and service providers read). The percentages show the proportional uplift that would need to be applied to the current APC

to maintain current total revenues. So, in example 8, the APCs charged in the USA by Publisher 4 would need to increase by 8% if they wanted to adopt more equitable pricing in one step for all customers while maintaining current revenue.

This is not the only way to address the shortfall, but it illustrates the magnitude of the issue. A more practical approach might be to gradually implement more equitable pricing over several years.

Exchange rates and currency

Finally, exchange rates are also a factor to consider when setting more equitable prices.

Either a price is set in the publisher's currency of choice and the customer shoulders the risks of currency fluctuation, or a price is set in local currency and the publisher takes the risk. If libraries and publishers are already used to dealing with pricing in one partner's choice of currency and are happy to do so, there is no reason to change what is working for both parties. However, exchange rates and currency fluctuations have been identified as a very significant pain point for libraries in many parts of the world⁷.

It is more stable and manageable for institutions in resource-limited countries for prices to be set in local currency. The risk of this approach turns out to be less than publisher intuition might suggest.

Publishers, especially larger ones, are better positioned to manage the risks of exchange rate fluctuations for three key reasons. First, for any given currency, the sums involved will represent the entire budget of institutions using that currency, whereas they are likely to represent a small part of the publisher's total revenue. Second, the risk to publishers is mitigated by being spread across a wide range of currencies: some fluctuations will disadvantage publishers, but some will benefit them, smoothing the overall impact. Third, larger publishers will have advice and options that give them sophisticated mechanisms for dealing with exchange rate fluctuations. *We modeled the impact of this approach and described this exercise in more detail in Appendix 4.*

Here's how managing fluctuations in exchange rates could work in practice:

1. The publisher sets global differentiated prices in US dollars (or their normal currency).
2. For the ALPHA, BETA, and GAMMA bands prices are translated into local currencies using the then-current exchange rates (or, for example, a three-month or six-month average).
3. Fixed prices for all bands are published and transparent.

⁷ Ellen Tise and Glenn Truran. 'Unbuckling the subscription model: a South African perspective.' (2019). [open.uct.ac.za
https://open.uct.ac.za/bitstream/handle/11427/30746/Unbuckling%20the%20Subscription%20Model-%20a%20South%20African%20Perspective%20-%206%20December%202019.pdf?sequence=1](https://open.uct.ac.za/bitstream/handle/11427/30746/Unbuckling%20the%20Subscription%20Model-%20a%20South%20African%20Perspective%20-%206%20December%202019.pdf?sequence=1)

4. The publisher invoices customers at the fixed price (in dollars or local currency according to the band).
5. Customers invoiced in dollars (or the publisher's normal currency) bear the cost of any currency exchange.
6. Customers invoiced in their local currency convert the amount into dollars for payment.
7. The publisher receives the money and bears the risk that the exchange rate has changed between price setting and payment receipt.

It may, however, be unreasonable to expect this from smaller publishers and service providers. The challenges of this approach are:

- There is some extra administrative burden on the publisher (e.g. in reconciling transactions that may differ slightly due to currency conversions and administrative fees).
- There are bank charges to factor in, and this will vary depending on which banks are involved.
- Publishers without financial reserves would face more risk, as losing even modest revenue could leave them struggling to support their journal.

The Equitable Pricing Tool

The tool is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/12780646>. It is an Excel spreadsheet that allows publishers and service providers interested in implementing more equitable pricing for existing services to explore the effects of different settings. The tool can also be used to derive figures for hybrid OA papers, or indeed for other sorts of pricing (e.g. subscriptions); however, note that it is probably advisable to separate full OA, hybrid, and subscription (or other papers) into different calculations, as the profile of countries from which the papers come are likely to vary.

The input required is the number of papers published (or projected) from each country, along with details of the waiver/discount regime currently in effect, if any. Users can then set their own bands, either trying out custom set-ups that might suit their circumstances or choosing from several preset options.

There are two simple outputs. The first shows any reduction in income that introducing banded differentiated pricing would incur. This is expressed as the percentage by which, for those settings and with that background data, the base price would need to increase to maintain present revenues. The second output demonstrates the sort of income fluctuations that would have been seen historically over several successive years had local currency pricing been in use.

Appendix 3, which we strongly encourage you to read, contains additional detail about how the Equitable Pricing Tool was created and how it can be used. It also provides examples from four anonymous but real publishers: two large mixed-model publishers, one medium mixed-model university press, and one medium-sized fully open-access publisher. These examples illustrate that different outcomes are achieved for each publisher depending on the geographic spread of their authors and the banding chosen.

Conclusion

We envisage there are at least three ways this framework could be used in practice.

- **As a conversation starter**

Librarians and funders can use the framework to start conversations with publishers and other service providers about whether more equitable global pricing has been considered and, if so, how the approach used aligns with or differs from this framework.

- **For new services**

The toolkit can be used by a publisher or other service provider to launch entirely new services with more equitable pricing from the outset.

- **To transition existing services**

Publishers and service providers will have a current revenue stream that they may need, or wish, to retain and they will also have a contribution to make. Stakeholders will need to agree on how any risk will be shared. Customers might find getting additional money to pay difficult or even impossible. The more equitable price in less well-off countries may be higher than current prices, particularly where there are currently full waivers. It may therefore take time to move all countries and customers to more equitable pricing, and different countries and different publishers may be able to move at different speeds.

We would emphasize that a transition to more equitable pricing will need to be done in close dialogue between publishers and their global customers so that the change is transparent and well supported and acceptable transition rules are agreed upon. Open, transparent, mutually agreeable, and flexible approaches are needed.

Data and Tool Availability

The Equitable Pricing Tool is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/12780646>.

Information about the datasets we explored and used is available in the Appendices which follow. This includes our analysis of different PPI providers, our analysis of all the ICP/World Bank PPI options, information about how the Equitable Pricing Tool was created and can be used, and data to guide currency selection.

Acknowledgments

We have appreciated and learned from the following people as we progressed through the project. We hasten to add that these people may not agree with all of the contents of this document or the framework. Thank you to:

Our Steering Group members

Geoffrey Boulton, Colleen Campbell, Robert Kiley, Iryna Kuchma, Nora Papp-Leroy, Johan Rooryck, and Bregt Saenen

Our interviewees and early readers

Katharina Baier, Rod Cookson, Adam Der, Richard Gallagher, Mandy Hill, Steven Inchcoombe, Malavika Legge, Niamh O’Conner, César Pallares, Kimberley Parker, Frances Pinter, César Rendon, Glenn Truran, Jeremy Upton, Charles Watkinson, and Stuart Whayman.

We are also grateful to Digital Science for access to Dimensions <https://www.digital-science.com/product/dimensions>.

Appendix 1 – Comparison of PPIs

Comparing PPI's	ICP / World Bank	Numbeo	Big Mac	United Nations Statistical Department	Eurostat / OECD
Coverage / Number of Countries	192 (2024), very complete	85 (2024), limited coverage particularly in less-populated or less-developed regions	53 (2024), some large areas are even taken as 1, like the Eurozone. And, depending on the presence of MacDonald's. E.g. almost no data for African countries.	Patchy coverage. Each country has to empower its statistical unit to participate and the country needs to be selected by UN-based researchers for some sort of project in order to be included.	Only EU / member countries. EU36 (all countries coordinated by the OECD).
Update Frequency / Latest Update	Once every 3-4 years, latest data end of 2021, published May 2024; next expected May 2027.	Does not have a fixed schedule for updates. Parts are updated depending on several factors, including the availability of new user-contributed data and the resources allocated by Numbeo for data maintenance and updates.	Semi-Annual, January & July, latest January 2024.	Very irregular, depending on the ongoing character of the academic research or country necessity.	Yearly in December for the EU36. Yearly estimates for current year in March for the EU27 Member States (based on full use of latest available price data).
Methodology & Limitations	Very sound and consistent method. Extensive on goods & services measured. Part of ICP (International Comparison Program). The indices are based on weighted baskets of goods and services, which may not accurately reflect the consumption patterns and preferences of all different countries.	The user-generated nature of the data means that it may not be a representative sample of the population (self-reporting bias). In general, there is a lack of methodological transparency.	Simplistic Approach: The Big Mac Index relies on a single product, the Big Mac burger. Furthermore, it is an economic indicator produced by a commercial magazine: The Economist.	The System of National Accounts (SNA 2008), provides guidelines and methodologies for calculating PPI's. Academic institutions and National Statistical Agencies utilize these standards to estimate PPI ratios for their respective countries.	Derived from the ICP / World Bank method. More detailed in specific EU-related categories.
Data Quality	Varies per country. In some cases, data may be outdated, incomplete, or subject to manipulation. Furthermore, it is typically calculated at the national level, which may overlook regional variations within countries that can be significant, particularly in large and diverse countries.	The data may be more readily available and reliable for popular cities or tourist destinations, while other areas may have insufficient or unreliable data. This affects accuracy.	Tends to favor countries with a strong presence of fast-food chains. This bias can skew the results and overlook the relative prices and purchasing power in countries where fast food is not as prevalent or where local food markets dominate.	Varies per research and country.	High quality, mostly well developed countries.

The graph below compares the ICP/World Bank GDP, Numbeo, and Big Mac PPIs, and highlights some peculiar differences. For the ZETA band countries, like the Nordics, North America, and Western Europe, the differences between the PPIs are quite trivial, but in other parts of the world the differences are large and problematic. GDP PPIs (shown in black) are seen to be similar for comparable pairs of countries, while the other measures show big differences (e.g. Big Mac shows big differences between Norway and Denmark, or between India and Pakistan, while Numbeo shows big differences between USA and Canada). This helps demonstrate that the World Bank GDP PPIs are more suitable for our purposes.

Appendix 2 – ICP/World Bank PPIs

The ICP uses a classification system known as the International Classification of Products by Activity (ICPA), which categorizes goods and services into various groups for the purpose of collecting and comparing price data across countries. The ICPA classification system consists of different levels, starting from broad categories down to more detailed subcategories. Each level represents a different level of aggregation and specificity in terms of the products and activities being classified.

Code / Name	11 Indicators Explained	Judgement
1000000:GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT	This ICP classification heading covers individual consumption expenditure by households; individual consumption expenditure by nonprofit institutions serving households (NPISHs); individual consumption expenditure by government; collective consumption expenditure by government; gross capital formation; balance of exports and imports.	Broad / Covers all, and broadly accepted
1300000:INDIVIDUAL CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE BY GOVERNMENT	This ICP classification heading covers individual consumption expenditures by government for Housing; Pharmaceutical products; Other medical products; Therapeutic appliances and equipment; Out-patient medical services; Out-patient dental services; Out-patient paramedical services; Hospital services; Compensation of employees - Ind. Hth. Govt; Intermediate consumption - Ind. Hth. Govt; Gross operating surplus - Ind. Hth. Govt; Net taxes on production - Ind. Hth. Govt; Receipts from sales - Ind. Hth. Govt; Recreation and culture; Education benefits and reimbursements; Compensation of employees - Ind. Edu. Govt; Intermediate consumption - Ind. Edu. Govt; Gross operating surplus - Ind. Edu. Govt; Net taxes on production - Ind. Edu. Govt; Receipt from sales - Ind. Edu. Govt; Social protection;	Too Specific in Medical
1400000:COLLECTIVE CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE BY GOVERNMENT	This ICP classification heading covers collective consumption expenditures by government for Compensation of employees - Coll. Govt; Intermediate consumption - Coll. Govt; Gross operating surplus - Coll. Govt; Net taxes on production - Coll. Govt; Receipts from sales - Coll. Govt.	Only specific Government expenditures
1501300:OTHER PRODUCTS	This ICP classification heading covers expenditures for Other products.	Only Consumer Goods
9020000:ACTUAL INDIVIDUAL CONSUMPTION	The total value of the individual consumption expenditures of households, nonprofit institutions serving households (NPISHs), and government at purchasers' prices.	This might be more commercially sound vs. GDP since it is at actual Purchaser's Price; covers all
9100000:HOUSEHOLDS AND NPISHS FINAL CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE	The total value of actual and imputed final consumption expenditures incurred by households and NPISHs on individual goods and services. It also includes expenditures on individual goods and services sold at prices that are not economically significant.	Broader in Services, but excluding Government
9120000:ACTUAL EDUCATION	Household expenditure on pre-primary, primary, secondary, postsecondary, and tertiary education plus expenditure of nonprofit institutions serving households (NPISHs) on education plus general government expenditure on education benefits and reimbursements and the production of education services.	Only Education, heavily off for some countries, because of certain specific local educational dynamics.
9140000:ACTUAL MISCELLANEOUS GOODS AND SERVICES	Household expenditure on personal care, personal effects, social protection, insurance, and financial and other services plus expenditure by nonprofit institutions serving households (NPISHs) on social protection and other services plus general government expenditure on social protection.	Very specific in social protection
9250000:DOMESTIC ABSORPTION	Actual individual consumption at purchasers' prices plus collective consumption expenditure by government at purchasers' prices plus gross capital formation at purchasers' prices.	Also at Purchaser's Prices, excluding Non-Profit, including heavy investments
9260000:INDIVIDUAL CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE BY HOUSEHOLDS WITHOUT HOUSING	The total value of actual and imputed final consumption expenditures incurred by households and NPISHs on individual goods and services, without housing related expenditures. It also includes expenditures on individual goods and services sold at prices that are not economically significant.	Excluding Government and Housing
9270000:GENERAL GOVERNMENT FINAL CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE	The total value of actual and imputed final consumption expenditures incurred by government on individual goods and services and final consumption expenditure of government on collective services.	Only Government

ICP-2021 Comparing 2 PPI's

ACCESSING THE DATA AND CALCULATING THE PPI VALUES

The data can be found and downloaded via this link: <http://databank.worldbank.org/source/icp-2021#>

On the left side of the screen, choose the 'Classification' tab. Select:

1. Market exchange rate (US\$ = 1) **and**
2. Purchasing power parity (PPP) (US\$ = 1)

Next, choose the 'Series' tab and select:

1. 1000000:GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT **and**
2. SP.EXCHG.RATE.ICP:Exchange Rate Value

Choose the 'Country' tab and select all countries by ticking the little box on the top left.

In the "Time" tab, select the data year(s), which in our case is 2021.

Finally, choose your data format from the 'Download Options' button at the top right of the screen. We used Excel but you may prefer a different format.

Using the downloaded data, for each country, divide the World Bank/ICP purchasing power-informed GDP values by the Exchange Rate values.

Appendix 3 – How to use the Equitable Pricing Tool

To build the Equitable Pricing Tool, we used Dimensions.ai to produce a list of all countries with at least one Gold OA publication⁸ in 2023, along with the number of papers for each country. We then added the ICP/World Bank GDP PPI value for each country to this list.

The Equitable Pricing Tool provides a worksheet for data input, where the number of OA papers by country can be entered and any discounts currently offered can be included (for ease, the Research4Life (R4L) discount structure can be selected from a dropdown menu). The dashboard includes a table allowing band boundaries to be set and a single adjusted PPI value to be assigned to every country within that band. For example, bands can be set from 0-0.2, 0.2-0.4, 0.4-0.6, and so on. The adjusted values for each band can be set however you choose, so for these three bands, the adjusted band values could be 0.1, 0.3, and 0.5 (i.e. set to the band midpoints), or 0.2, 0.4, and 0.6 (i.e. set to the band ceiling), or any other structure.

The Equitable Pricing Tool then checks each country's PPI value, determines which band it falls into using the current settings, and assigns an adjusted PPI value. For example, Ecuador has a PPI of 0.45, so this would fall into the 0.4-0.6 band (if the bands are set up as in our example), and result in an adjusted PPI of 0.5 (midpoint) or 0.6 (ceiling).

The tool derives a total nominal value for the global revenue derived from those papers (pre-banding) by taking the total number of papers, with appropriate allowance for any existing discount structure, and multiplying by a nominal APC figure. (The actual APC value is irrelevant, as we are interested only in ratios and the number eventually cancels out.)

The new nominal revenue after banding is calculated by multiplying the number of papers for each country by the adjusted PPI for that country and the nominal APC, and then summing across all countries. This figure can then be easily compared with the original revenue figure, and the change in APC that would be needed to generate the same income after banding is calculated and presented as a percentage increase.

Although the tool is optimized for APCs, it could easily be adapted for use with other revenue streams.

There are some obvious simplifications in this modelling:

⁸ Dimensions defines Gold OA thus: 'Publication is published in a fully open access journal (this includes all publications with a Gold OA status in Unpaywall and those on our own fully OA list of journals).' Note that our calculations primarily concern ratios; if the profile of country splits is similar, variations in precise definitions will have little impact on the estimates. Users of the tool we have developed will be able to use whatever definitions they need to.

- It is based on one year’s worth of volume data (2023). However, a publisher using the tool could model as many years’ worth of data as needed.
- Our examples take the Dimensions data at face value.
- Our modelling takes no account of a possible increase in submissions resulting from adopting more equitable pricing.
- For the sake of this analysis, the tool also ignores currency exchange fluctuations (these are considered in Appendix 4).
- The examples we have given ignore variations in pricing due to negotiated consortial deals. However, publishers using the tool could easily factor these in.

Dimensions includes papers from 59 ‘countries’ that do not have a World Bank GDP PPI figure because they aren’t actually separate countries (e.g. Gibraltar and Jersey) or because they do not supply data to the World Bank (e.g. North Korea). Collectively the numbers of papers involved is trivial, accounting for 0.3% of all OA papers published. We have categorized these in these ways:

- Any currently appearing on the Research4Life Group A list⁹ were assigned a starting PPI value of zero – i.e. they will always fall into the ALPHA band and take the value set for the ALPHA band.
- Any with a close political affiliation to a larger country were assigned the PPI value of the ‘parent’ country (e.g. Vatican City to Italy, Gibraltar and Jersey to the UK).
- We assigned Liechtenstein a high PPI value as it has one of the highest gross domestic products per person in the world.
- Bonaire, Saint Eustatius, and Saba were allocated a PPI based on the average of Curacao, Sint Maartin, and Aruba).

Table 2. PPIs and total Gold OA output in 2023 by country. (Note that this table only shows the articles published in fully OA journals because more open access articles by authors from lower PPI countries publish in these journals. Publishers can model the impact of publications in both fully OA and hybrid journals using the Equitable Pricing Tool).

Country	2021 PPI	Gold OA publications
Liechtenstein	1.3	44
Bermuda	1.22	40
Barbados	1.19	164
Cayman Islands	1.17	24
Switzerland	1.14	19,695

⁹ <https://www.research4life.org/access/eligibility/#groupa>

Israel	1.13	7370
Iceland	1.12	790
Turks and Caicos Islands	1.09	10
British Virgin Islands	1.07	11
Australia	1.06	32,161
Cocos Islands	1.06	1
Norfolk Island	1.06	61
Norway	1.04	10,381
Svalbard and Jan Mayen	1.04	28
New Zealand	1.03	4835
Faroe Islands	1.01	64
Antarctica	1	2
Micronesia	1	13
United States	1	197,631
Denmark	0.99	10,569
Bahamas	0.98	48
Luxembourg	0.97	865
Sweden	0.97	16,076
Canada	0.94	37,877
Aland Islands	0.93	18
Finland	0.93	7260
Japan	0.9	52,236
British Indian Ocean Territory	0.89	0
Falkland Islands	0.89	17
Gibraltar	0.89	38
Guernsey	0.89	1
Ireland	0.89	6238
Isle of Man	0.89	4
Jersey	0.89	23
United Kingdom	0.89	67,317
Netherlands	0.87	21,274

Austria	0.84	10,234
Greenland	0.84	79
San Marino	0.84	34
Belgium	0.83	12,512
Germany	0.83	57,928
France	0.81	32,656
French Guiana	0.81	89
French Polynesia	0.81	61
French Southern Territories	0.81	0
Guadeloupe	0.81	71
Martinique	0.81	50
Mayotte	0.81	11
Monaco	0.81	102
New Caledonia	0.81	76
Reunion	0.81	158
Saint Barthelemy	0.81	1
Saint Martin	0.81	6
Wallis and Futuna	0.81	0
Sint Maarten	0.8	61
Anguilla	0.78	21
Aruba	0.76	32
Bonaire, Saint Eustatius and Saba	0.76	11
China	0.76	298,143
Netherlands Antilles	0.76	1
Italy	0.73	56,868
Vatican	0.73	8
Andorra	0.72	28
Curacao	0.72	103
South Korea	0.72	41,477
Spain	0.7	49058
Cyprus	0.68	2123

Saint Kitts and Nevis	0.68	143
Antigua and Barbuda	0.67	113
Kuwait	0.67	1458
Malta	0.65	470
Palestinian Territory	0.65	1060
Uruguay	0.65	1123
Grenada	0.64	294
Portugal	0.64	15,526
United Arab Emirates	0.64	6848
Slovenia	0.63	3375
Estonia	0.62	1447
Greece	0.62	11,587
Qatar	0.61	2785
Montserrat	0.6	6
Singapore	0.6	6908
Slovakia	0.58	3890
Trinidad and Tobago	0.58	255
Latvia	0.57	1583
Chile	0.56	8035
Czechia	0.55	8163
Saint Lucia	0.55	38
Zimbabwe	0.54	672
Belize	0.53	45
Costa Rica	0.53	1148
Dominica	0.53	44
Haiti	0.53	74
Jamaica	0.53	171
Maldives	0.53	86
Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	0.53	60
Cabo Verde	0.52	46
Djibouti	0.51	43

Lithuania	0.51	3077
Saudi Arabia	0.51	32,154
Taiwan	0.51	15,386
Oman	0.5	1563
Panama	0.5	363
Seychelles	0.5	30
South Africa	0.5	14,044
Bahrain	0.49	699
Hungary	0.49	6686
Mexico	0.49	14,351
Croatia	0.48	4865
Comoros	0.46	45
Jordan	0.46	4410
Ecuador	0.45	3140
Namibia	0.45	322
Peru	0.45	4507
Poland	0.45	31,266
Brazil	0.44	64,889
Central African Republic	0.44	80
Fiji	0.44	163
Gabon	0.44	163
Honduras	0.44	395
Liberia	0.44	100
Morocco	0.44	4728
Western Sahara	0.44	2
Botswana	0.43	450
El Salvador	0.43	317
Guyana	0.43	59
Turkmenistan	0.43	40
Bulgaria	0.42	3311
Democratic Republic of the Congo	0.42	674

Lesotho	0.42	96
Sao Tome and Principe	0.42	22
Equatorial Guinea	0.41	16
Guatemala	0.41	245
Ivory Coast	0.41	545
Serbia	0.41	4936
Serbia and Montenegro	0.41	14
South Sudan	0.41	64
Argentina	0.4	7062
Brunei	0.4	528
Eswatini	0.4	95
Mauritius	0.4	161
Republic of the Congo	0.4	274
Albania	0.39	466
Bosnia and Herzegovina	0.39	1134
Chad	0.39	90
Dominican Republic	0.39	329
Kenya	0.39	3259
Libya	0.39	440
Montenegro	0.39	331
Paraguay	0.39	294
Philippines	0.39	3127
Romania	0.39	10,477
Somalia	0.39	253
Timor Leste	0.39	72
Benin	0.38	606
Iraq	0.38	10,677
Kosovo	0.38	399
Niger	0.38	184
Senegal	0.38	736
Ghana	0.37	3805

Guinea-Bissau	0.37	29
Lebanon	0.37	2539
Malawi	0.37	769
Malaysia	0.37	16,130
Mali	0.37	311
Nigeria	0.37	8683
Bolivia	0.36	262
Burkina Faso	0.36	671
Togo	0.36	231
Cambodia	0.35	494
Cameroon	0.35	1584
Colombia	0.35	8457
Mozambique	0.35	589
Thailand	0.35	10,951
Indonesia	0.34	84,593
Moldova	0.34	351
North Macedonia	0.34	615
Uganda	0.34	2351
Bangladesh	0.33	8028
Eritrea	0.33	51
Mauritania	0.33	56
Sierra Leone	0.33	223
Tanzania	0.33	1934
Guinea	0.32	186
Russia	0.32	42,177
Zambia	0.32	694
Burundi	0.31	99
Laos	0.31	191
Mongolia	0.31	492
Tunisia	0.31	3384
Turkey	0.31	43,936

Vietnam	0.31	5739
Kazakhstan	0.3	3545
Nicaragua	0.3	321
Rwanda	0.3	678
Algeria	0.29	2603
Armenia	0.29	640
Gambia	0.29	221
Angola	0.28	165
Ethiopia	0.28	7487
India	0.28	68,610
Sri Lanka	0.28	2165
Azerbaijan	0.27	938
Belarus	0.27	1410
Bhutan	0.27	128
Georgia	0.27	754
Iran	0.27	24,226
Nepal	0.27	4116
Pakistan	0.27	17,789
Ukraine	0.27	16,820
Suriname	0.26	31
Egypt	0.25	21,612
Kyrgyzstan	0.24	377
Myanmar	0.24	263
Uzbekistan	0.24	3669
Sudan	0.23	1204
Tajikistan	0.22	131
Afghanistan	0.17	447
Cook Islands	0	7
Cuba	0	678
Kiribati	0	9
Marshall Islands	0	5

Nauru	0	1
Niue	0	0
North Korea	0	59
Palau	0	13
Papua New Guinea	0	180
Saint Helena	0	13
Samoa	0	38
Solomon Islands	0	21
Syria	0	973
Tokelau	0	2
Tonga	0	30
Tuvalu	0	2
Vanuatu	0	11
Venezuela	0	620
Yemen	0	953
Total		1,826,723

Example 2. Banding in 0.1, mid-points

Lower	Upper	Band value
0	0.1	0.05
0.1	0.2	0.15
0.2	0.3	0.25
0.3	0.4	0.35
0.4	0.5	0.45
0.5	0.6	0.55
0.6	0.7	0.65
0.7	0.8	0.75

0.8	0.9	0.85
0.9	1	0.95
1	1.1	1.05
1.1	1.2	1.15
1.2	1.37	1.25
1.37	1.37	1.35

Example 3. Banding in 0.1, band value takes upper limit

Lower	Upper	Band value
0	0.1	0.1
0.1	0.2	0.2
0.2	0.3	0.3
0.3	0.4	0.4
0.4	0.5	0.5
0.5	0.6	0.6
0.6	0.7	0.7
0.7	0.8	0.8
0.8	0.9	0.9
0.9	1	1
1	1.1	1.1
1.1	1.2	1.2
1.2	1.37	1.37
1.37	1.37	1.37

Example 4. Bandings in 0.2, band value takes upper limit

Lower	Upper	Band value
0	0.2	0.2
0.2	0.4	0.4
0.4	0.6	0.6
0.6	0.8	0.8
0.8	1	1
1	1.2	1.2
1.2	1.37	1.37

Example 5. Bandings in 0.2, band values more nuanced

Lower	Upper	Band value
0	0.2	0.2
0.2	0.4	0.3
0.4	0.6	0.5
0.6	0.8	0.8
0.8	1	1
1	1.2	1.1
1.2	1.37	1.3

Example 6. Bandings in 0.2, band values more nuanced (v2)

Lower	Upper	Band value
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0	0.2	0.2
0.2	0.4	0.3
0.4	0.6	0.5
0.6	0.8	0.8
0.8	1	1
1	1.2	1.2
1.2	1.37	1.37

Example 7. Bandings more finely spaced at top and bottom, wider in middle, bands take top value

Lower	Upper	Band value
0	0.1	0.1
0.1	0.2	0.2
0.2	0.3	0.3
0.3	0.4	0.4
0.4	0.6	0.6
0.6	0.8	0.8
0.8	1	1
1	1.1	1.1
1.1	1.2	1.2
1.2	1.37	

Example 8. Bandings in 0.2, upper limit, top band set to 1 (i.e. nobody pays more than the default US rate)

Lower	Upper	Band value
0	0.2	0.2
0.2	0.4	0.4
0.4	0.6	0.6
0.6	0.8	0.8
0.8	1	1
1	1.2	1

Appendix 4 – Exchange rates and currency selection

The framework offers an objective way to set differentiated global pricing and also to assess the impact of billing some or all customers in their local currency. Since downward fluctuations in some currencies tend to be balanced out by upwards fluctuations in others, the risk of this approach turns out to be less than publisher intuition might suggest.

We assume here that prices are set in the local currency at the usual time for price setting and apply without change through the whole of the following year, with the publisher taking on the risk that exchange rate fluctuations will lower the value (in the publisher's currency) of the set price. In practice, the price is likely to be set using a three-month or six-month average rate, and overall that should not affect the calculations much. We also assume for the purpose of this exercise that APCs (or other fees) paid throughout the following year are converted into dollars at that year's average rate. In aggregate this should be the case, and the more papers that are published throughout the year in that country (and thus, the more important that country is in its contribution to the calculations), the more likely this is to be an accurate approximation.

The risk to overall income is determined by two factors: the proportion of overall income that comes from each country, and the volatility of that country's currency. We used the Digital Science Dimensions¹⁰ database to establish Gold OA article volumes by country for 2023 (as we are looking forward to potential future risks, the most up-to-date profile of publications is the relevant one to use). We looked at data both across the board and for the same four specific publishers selected as examples in the main body of the report.

This enabled us to estimate the proportion of the total revenue that would be generated by countries in each of the bands, considering the reduced prices in those bands resulting from the application of the framework.

Next, we explored the magnitude of individual currency fluctuations averaged across all countries. We used World Bank data (<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/PA.NUS.FCRF>) for average exchange rates year by year, from 2013 to 2022 (the most recent year available). The data is incomplete for a few countries, with several lacking 2022 data and others showing gaps or lacking any data at all. These were excluded from the country-by-country analysis. Of these excluded countries, only authors in Iran had published significant numbers of papers.

The calculation proceeded as follows. The number of OA papers published from each country was added to the currency tables, along with the country's band (for the calculations below, we

¹⁰ We are grateful to Digital Science for access to Dimensions (<https://www.digital-science.com/product/dimensions/>).

had band settings as per Example 4 of Appendix 3). For each successive year, the proportional change in exchange rate for each country was weighted by the number of papers for that country, and the totals for the year were summed by band across countries. The annual totals can then be compared to show how exchange rate variations impact across the board. Looking at this across a ten-year range allows us to exclude the possibility that any single year was a particularly unstable year for currencies. We looked at the maximum year-on-year rate drops and increases over that period and took an average across the whole period.

For illustration purposes, the table below shows how this looks for a small portion of the data. Looking at the Papua New Guinea (PNG) kina, for example, the exchange rate shifted from US\$1 = PNK2.24 in 2013 to PNK2.46 in 2014. The number of papers from PNG is 180, so the relative contribution of Papua New Guinea to the total revenue drops from 180 in 2013 to 164 in 2014. In our little table here, Papua New Guinea is the only ALPHA band country, so the impact on revenue for that band is -8.8%. In other words, publishers setting a Papua New Guinea rate in PNK in 2013 will see 8.8% less revenue than anticipated in 2014 due to currency shifts.

Country	No. Pubs, 2022	Band	Local currency = \$1			Weighted value per \$1		
			2013	2014	2015	2013	2014	2015
Vietnam	5739	Beta	20933	21148	21698	5739	5681	5594
Indonesia	84593	Beta	10461	11865	13389	84593	74583	74963
Papua New Guinea	180	Alpha	2.24	2.46	2.77	180	164	160
Uzbekistan	3669	Beta	2095	2311	2568	3669	3326	3302
Chile	8035	Gamma	495	570	654	8035	6977	7006
Band Alpha total						180	164	160
Change year on year							8.8%	11.1%
Bands Alpha and Beta total						94,181	83,754	84,019
Change year on year							11.1%	10.8%
Bands Alpha, Beta and Gamma total								
Change year on year						102,216	90,732	91,025
							11.2%	10.9%

Across all the data, we end with the results for the year-on-year changes shown below:

	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Max	Min	Average
Alpha	-1.6%	-6.8%	-13.8%	0.0%	19.8%	-37.6%	-23.4%	-19.3%	-8.8%	19.8%	-37.6%	-10.2%
Alpha + Beta	-9.2%	-14.4%	-6.6%	-3.2%	-6.9%	-4.4%	-6.1%	-3.6%	-10.7%	-3.2%	-14.4%	-7.2%
Alpha+Beta+Gamma	-7.6%	-14.2%	-5.8%	-0.5%	-5.3%	-4.6%	-7.1%	-2.1%	-8.4%	-0.5%	-14.2%	-6.2%

We constructed similar tables for each of the publishers we looked at, using their country data for the weightings. (Note that while for clarity we show results here for just the ALPHA, BETA, and GAMMA bands in one particular band setting, the Equitable Pricing Tool generates figures across all bands for any given band setting.)

The second part of the calculation involves estimating what proportion of the total revenue (or each publisher's total revenue) is affected by these changes. This is a simple matter of weighting the number of papers for each country by the PPI value assigned for its band,

summing those figures across the band, and then dividing by the total for all bands. This gives us the following:

	% income in Band Alpha	% income in Band Beta	% income in Band Gamma	Alpha + Beta	Alpha + Beta + Gamma
Total	0.1%	13.9%	10.7%	14.0%	24.7%
Publisher 1	0.1%	8.7%	7.0%	8.8%	15.8%
Publisher 2	0.1%	5.7%	4.3%	5.7%	10.1%
Publisher 3	0.1%	9.1%	7.2%	9.2%	16.4%
Publisher 4	0.1%	2.8%	3.4%	2.9%	6.3%

Combining the two sets of data, we can produce estimates for the effect on total revenue of pricing in local currency, whether that is applied to the ALPHA band alone, or additional bands as well. We illustrate this here for the first three bands:

Projected income fluctuations due to XR changes				
		Maximum	Minimum	Average
Total	Alpha	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	Alpha and Beta	-0.4%	-2.0%	-1.0%
	Alpha, Beta and Gamma	-0.1%	-3.5%	-1.5%
Publisher 1	Alpha	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	Alpha and Beta	-0.3%	-1.1%	-0.6%
	Alpha, Beta and Gamma	-0.3%	-1.6%	-0.9%
Publisher 2	Alpha	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	Alpha and Beta	-0.2%	-0.7%	-0.4%
	Alpha, Beta and Gamma	-0.1%	-1.1%	-0.6%
Publisher 3	Alpha	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	Alpha and Beta	-0.3%	-1.0%	-0.6%
	Alpha, Beta and Gamma	-0.1%	-1.9%	-0.9%
Publisher 4	Alpha	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	Alpha and Beta	-0.1%	-0.3%	-0.2%
	Alpha, Beta and Gamma	0.0%	-0.7%	-0.3%

This table shows the maximum annual changes (positive and negative) that would have been experienced over this period, along with the average over the whole period. So, for example, if Publisher 2 were to adopt local currency for countries in ALPHA, BETA, and GAMMA bands, on the basis of the swings experienced over the past decade they might expect annual swings

in budgeted global income of -0.1%% to -1.1%, with an average of -0.6%. A one-off price increase of 0.6% in the first year would mitigate this (on average) in perpetuity.

Note that these calculations ignore any possible increases in revenue generated by applying the framework itself (i.e. one would hope that more equitable pricing would encourage an overall increase in volumes). The numbers here are small enough that if such an increase were seen to any significant degree, the resulting revenue could easily outweigh even the most disadvantageous currency swings.

These calculations are built into the Equitable Pricing Tool, since they require no additional data to perform. For any given banding setting, the tool gives an estimate of the risk involved in offering prices set in local currency for any level of banding.